

Water-tightness Airborne Detection Implementation

D7.1 LCA Report

Authors: CIRCE

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Executive Summary

This deliverable contains the results obtained from the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of the two WADI units developed in the project: MAV and UAV. To develop this analysis, it was applied the methodology described in ISO 14040:2006.

The main objectives of this deliverable can be summarized in the following points:

- Perform an inventory analysis by means of quantifying all the energy and material flows, as well as the incoming and outgoing materials (extracted or emitted into the environment) required during the manufacturing processes of the new WADI units and the useful lifetime of the demonstrators involved in the project.
- Calculation of the most relevant environmental impacts indicators associated with the WADI water leaks detection techniques in order to be compared with the potential environmental improvements that could be achieved thanks to the WADI project development.

As main conclusions obtained from this study, when the MAV unit is analysed, the results obtained are depicted in the figure below. The carbon footprint of this unit is about 270,000 kg CO₂eq and the water footprint is 158,000 m³. The greatest contributor to most of the environmental categories is the impact associated with the fuel consumed during the aircraft flights. Besides, it is very relevant the contribution of the plane manufacturing over some indicators such as freshwater eutrophication and water depletion, and the contribution of the IR camera over the human toxicity indicator.

Relative environmental impact per indicator of the MAV WADI unit

Regarding the UAV unit, its carbon footprint is 545 kg CO₂eq and the water footprint is about 7,300 m³. The relative environmental impact of the UAV components, as well as the impacts of the consumption involved during the use stage are depicted in the figure below. The drone batteries have the greatest contribution in many environmental categories such as ozone depletion, human toxicity or metal depletion. This fact is mainly caused by the periodicity with which the batteries must be replaced along the lifetime of the drone. On the other hand, the electricity consumption required to charge the batteries has the greatest impact in the climate change indicator and in the water and fossil fuel depletion indicators. In this case, it is very important to specify the electricity mix of which country is used because the results can significantly vary.

Relative environmental impact per indicator of the UAV WADI unit (Portuguese electricity mix)

Finally, if the results obtained from the LCA studies are compared with the potential impacts that could be achieved by the WADI technology through a successful business model, the environmental opportunities presented by the WADI water leaks detection techniques are huge and the burdens associate with the manufacturing and the using stages of both systems are small in comparison to the environmental benefits achieved.

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1 Introduction

The main objective of WADI project is to contribute to the reduction of water losses in water transmission systems and to decrease the related energy consumption required for the process.

Water is increasingly becoming more valuable due to scarcity in many regions. This is the reason why the status of the transmission and distribution systems is a key factor to assure enough quantity and quality of water in Europe.

WADI project aims to investigate a new water detection technique deployed on two platforms (manned & unmanned) in order to achieve a better analysis of European water network. This technique is based on innovative optical remote sensing integrated in aircrafts. It consists of **manned aircraft flights (MAV)** and, **unmanned flights (UAV)** using **drones** equipped also with **two different optical devices (multispectral and IR cameras)**.

Water leaks detection using WADI technique is expected to increase water availability and thus, avoid resources depletion and environmental impacts related to the energy consumption of water networks. In this sense, performing an environmental evaluation of these detection methods is crucial to assess how the implementation of WADI technique affects different environmental categories such as climate change or water depletion.

2 LCA methodology

The **Life Cycle Analysis methodology (LCA)** is useful for analysing the environmental impact caused by any type of process and product [5]. The society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (SETAC) defines LCA as “an objective process to evaluate the environmental burdens associated with a product, processor activity by identifying energy and materials used and wastes released to the environment, and to evaluate and implement opportunities to achieve environmental improvements”. In other words, LCA studies cover the environmental aspects and potential impacts throughout a product’s life (i.e. cradle-to-grave) from raw material acquisition, via production and use phases, to waste management.

Regulation of the development of good quality LCA studies is compiled in standard UNE-EN ISO 14040:2006 [1]. Here, it is specified that a LCA is usually performed following four main stages, see Figure 2-1:

1. Goal and scope definition
2. Inventory analysis
3. Environmental impacts evaluation
4. Interpretation

Figure 2-1: Main stages of a LCA study.

The **goal and scope definition** stage is the first step in a LCA study in which the product or process to be assessed is defined, and so is the context of the study. The importance of this stage lies in the crucial connection between the purpose of the study and the system boundaries definition.

In this stage, many parameters have to be identified: time and resources needed, purpose of the study, intended application, system boundaries, methodology and general assumptions and limitations [2]. The most important points to be analyzed and fixed in this stage are the **system boundaries** and the **functional unit** (a quantitative description of the service performance of the case study or a quantitative description of products).

After this stage, the **inventory analysis** (LCI) is performed by means of data collection in collaboration with all the partners involved in the project. This data collection is restricted to the system boundaries previously identified.

Finally, stages 3 and 4 consist on the **environmental assessment** by itself. The environmental impact is determined for a serial of selected indicators, which are related to the calculation method applied in the study. Results of this analysis have, in the last phase of the LCA, to be **interpreted** to firstly summarize LCI and LCA results and then, discussed and reviewed to obtain conclusions, recommendations, depending on the goal and scope definition.

3 Environmental analysis

3.1 Goal scope and functional unit definition

The objective of this task is to perform an environmental analysis of both leak detection technologies. For the manned aircraft, **raw materials** extraction and processing, aircraft **manufacturing**, **use** phase and **end-of-life** strategies were included in the analysis. These phases were selected as the most “*impacting*” ones according to literature [4].

As an example of LCA studies applied to aircrafts, **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.** Figure 3-1 shows the flow diagram of an aircraft life cycle [3]. Different phases are identified in the diagram, as well as the different resources that are consumed in each stage.

Figure 3-1: Flow diagram of the A33-200 life cycle [3]

Finally, regarding the **functional unit**, Table 3-1 includes those selected for the analysed technologies within the framework of WADI project.

Detection technique	Functional unit
Manned aircraft	1 aircraft WADI unit (TECNAM P2006T+platform+cameras)
Drone	1 drone WADI unit (Model GG-X4+cameras)

Table 3-1: Functional unit considered for each WADI detection system

3.2 System boundaries

The system boundaries of the analyses performed in WP7 were set considering both the information available and the characteristics of the leak detection task itself. As foreground process, this is, those processes from which data can be directly measured and collected from the responsible companies, the analysis considered the manufacturing and use stages. On the other hand, the background processes, or what is the same, the processes defined by means of generic data taken from life cycle inventory databases, e.g. from commercial databases, were the raw material extraction and transformation, and the end-of-life strategies. Figure 3-2 depicts a scheme for an aircraft life cycle, taking into account from the materials extraction to the end-of-life of the aircraft.

Figure 3-2: Aircraft life cycle [6]

As mentioned above, a cradle-to-grave analysis was performed to both leak detection techniques. On the one hand, and in order to better identify the contribution of each component to the total environmental burden of the WADI solutions, a more detailed evaluation of the manufacturing stage was carried out. On the other hand, the most common end-of-life strategies have been identified and described in the last part of this deliverable, but the impact associated with them has not been quantitatively calculated. In this light, the current deliverable includes a cradle to gate evaluation of both the MAV and UAV units.

Regarding LCA impacts calculation, the study was performed according to ReCiPe Midpoint (H) V1.08 / Europe Recipe H method, excluding infrastructures. Nevertheless, infrastructures had to be considered in the UAV electric motor impacts analysis because this component is classified as infrastructure by Ecoinvent. The electric motor of the drone was the only one analysed including infrastructures because the impacts analysis without infrastructures was more representative.

Finally, since the direct electricity consumption is a critical LCI parameter that can significantly influence the environmental burden of the drone use stage, this study has considered the electric mix in the country where the flights take place. In consequence, the French and Portuguese mix of electricity have been taken into account.

3.3 Environmental impact indicators

The environmental analysis was performed by using midpoint approach impact category indicators. The different impact categories of the ReCiPe method and the measurement units that can be calculated are shown in Table 3-2.

Table 3-2: Impact categories included within the ReCiPe method and their units

Environmental impact category	Units
Climate change	kg CO₂ eq
Ozone depletion potential	kg CFC-11 eq
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO₂ eq
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq
Photochemical oxidant formation	kg NMVOC
Particulate matter formation	kg PM10 eq
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq
Ionising radiation	kBq U ₂₃₅ eq
Agricultural land occupation	m ² a
Urban land occupation	m ² a
Natural land transformation	m ²
Water depletion	m³
Metal depletion	kg Fe eq
Fossil depletion	kg oil eq

Eight of these indicators are marked in bold because they are considered as the most relevant indicators for this project [8] and they will be analysed with more detail along this deliverable. These indicators are:

- **Climate Change:** It is a major global problem nowadays, and reducing this impact is one of the main achievements that are expected out of this project. It is measured in kg of CO₂ equivalent referred to the functional unit of this analysis.
- **Ozone Depletion Potential** accounts for the destruction of the stratospheric ozone layer by anthropogenic emissions of ozone depleting substances and uses CFC-11 (trichlorofluoromethane) as a reference compound.
- **Terrestrial Acidification** is a measure of emissions that cause acidifying effects to the environment. It is expressed as kg SO₂ equivalent that provides an equivalent estimate of air pollutants emission. The major acidifying emissions are nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and sulphur dioxide (SO₂).
- **Eutrophication of Fresh Water** can be defined as the over-enrichment of watercourses with ammonia, nitrates, nitrogen oxides and phosphorous. Its occurrence can lead to damage of ecosystems, increasing mortality of aquatic fauna and flora and to loss of species dependent on low-nutrient environments. Eutrophication potential is expressed using the reference compound in kg PO₄ equivalents.
- **Human Toxicity:** This indicator assesses the effect of a chemical in function of the environmental persistence (fate), the accumulation in the human food chain

(exposure) and toxicity (effect) of the chemical. It is measured in kg 1,4 dichlorobenzene (1,4-DB eq.).

- **Water depletion:** Water consumption is the use of water in such a way that water is evaporated, incorporated into products, transferred to other watersheds, or disposed into the sea. Water that has been consumed is, thus, not available anymore in the watershed of origin for humans nor for ecosystems.
- **Metal depletion:** This indicator is related with mineral resource scarcity. It represents is the surplus ore potential.
- **Fossil depletion:** The characterization factor of fossil resource scarcity is the fossil fuel potential, based on the higher heating value. The unit is kg oil equivalents.

All the previous indicators can be included into the category of midpoint indicators. Midpoints can be defined as links in the cause-effect chains of an impact category. On the other hand, endpoints are related with the relative importance of emissions or extractions [7]. Figure 3-3 depicts the relationships between all the midpoint impact categories and the endpoint categories: damage to human health, damage to ecosystems and damage to resource availability. In this study, midpoints were selected to be calculated since they are more representative of the environmental mechanisms.

Figure 3-3: Representation of the relations between the impact categories midpoint and the areas of protection (endpoint) [8]

3.4 Software and databases

The environmental analysis was performed using a software and some databases included in the former. Besides the database developed in the framework of WADI

project, which compiles the information provided by partners, some extra literature data were also used.

SIMAPRO 8.5 was the software chosen to develop the LCA study. It is a flexible and well-designed tool for these analyses, based on ISO 14040. This software can simulate complex parametric models in different scenarios and calculate sensitivity analysis and statistical analysis.

On the other hand, the databases chosen for this work were:

- **ECOINVENT database:** developed by ETH (Swiss Research Institute). It deals with energy generation, mineral resource extraction and basic industrial processes, waste treatment and transport [9].
- The **European reference Life Cycle Database (ELCD)** is a database established by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) and integrated in the SimaPro LCA Software [10]. The ELCD database contains data from industries such as the chemical and metal industry. It also includes data on energy production, transport and end-of-life processes. The datasets are provided and approved by their respective industry associations.

4 Aircrafts LCI

Once the scope and system boundaries are defined, the next step to perform a Life Cycle Assessment analysis is to elaborate an inventory (LCI) of the different components and materials included in each stage. For this purpose, the LCI has been divided into two sections: the first one considers all the components and consumptions required to manufacture on unit of MAV or UAV; this analysis is called as cradle to gate study. On the other hand, the second section considers all the consumptions incurred during the use stage of each WADI unit, as well as the lifetime of each component and its replacement period.

4.1 Manned Aircraft Vehicle (MAV) LCI

4.1.1 MAV manufacturing LCI

As it was previously defined, the first leak detection technique consists of manned aircraft flights to monitor large areas by long-distance flights and important infrastructure. LCI of the MAV manufacturing was performed considering as **functional unit one unit of aircraft** with all the **cameras and instrumentation** required for the water leaks detection.

In order to illustrate the materials that are included in the Life Cycle Inventory, Figure 4-1 shows a picture of the aircraft selected for the WADI project; Figure 4-2 presents an scheme of the camera integration platform for the MAV and Figure 4-3 depicts two pictures of both selected cameras: multispectral and infra-red.

Figure 4-1: Aircraft TECNAM 2006T. Source: [11]

Figure 4-2: Camera integration platform

Figure 4-3: Left: Multispectral Camera SpectroCam [12]. Right: IR Camera NoxCam 640L [13]

The gathered information for the Manned Aircraft (MAV) is included from Table 4-1 to Table 4-5. The first of them (Table 4-1) is referred to technical specifications of the manned aircraft itself, Table 4-2 includes the inertial measurement unit information,

Table 4-3 and

Table 4-4 depict the components and materials of the multispectral and IR cameras respectively and Table 4-5 shows the information regarding the integration platform.

Table 4-1: Technical characteristics and components of the Manned Aircraft

	TECNAM P2006T	Value	Unit
General information	Empty Weight ¹	800	kg
	Maximum Weight	1230	kg
	Expected lifetime (from now)	22	years
Materials of construction	Aluminium alloy (main material)	718	kg
	Glass	2	kg
	Fuselage	N/A	kg
	Electronics and computer	30	kg
	Landing gear	50	kg
Engines (75 kW)	Engines	2	units
	Power of engines	75	kW
	Type of fuel	Avgas100ll or EN228 premium	
	Consumption during flight	38	l/h

¹ The value of empty weight is referred to the aircraft without cameras, fuel, passengers or any other load and the maximum weight is related to the load it can support.

Table 4-2: Technical characteristics and components of the Inertial Measurement Unit MAV

Name		Value	Unit
Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) and GPS Spatial dual EK – Advanced Navigation	Size	90*127*31	mm*mm*mm
	Power consumption	2.64	W
	Total weight	0.285	kg
	Expected lifetime (max uses)	10	years
Materials	Case (plastic)	0.057	kg
	Electronics and cable	0.228	kg

Table 4-3: Technical characteristics and components of the Multispectral Camera MAV

Name		Value	Unit
Multispectral camera SpectroCam VIS 1,4MP VNIR	Power consumption	10	W
	Size	138*124*98	mm*mm*mm
	Total weight	0.8	kg
	Present lifetime	6	years
	Expected lifetime (maximum uses)	N/A	years
Materials	Lenses	0.4	kg
	Lenses protector (plastic)	0.05	kg

Table 4-4: Technical characteristics and components of the IR Camera MAV

Name		Value	Unit
IR Camera NOXCAM 640L	Type	Cooled LWIR	
	Size	360*120*113	mm*mm*mm
	Power consumption	25-40	W
	Total weight	3,3	kg
	Expected lifetime (max uses)	8500	hours
Materials	Lenses	0.3	kg
	Infrared	0.57	kg
	Electronics and cable	0.33	kg

Table 4-5: Technical characteristics and components of the Integration Platform MAV

Name		Value	Unit
Integration platform	Weight total	11.12	kg
	Size	340X275X360	m*m*m
	Power consumption	NA	W
	Expected lifetime	>10<20	years

Materials	Electricity for construction	1.1	kWh
	GB-85 motor	0.72	kg
	BaseCamBGC Pro	0.93	kg
	Nuvo-5000E/P	4.4	kg
	Spatial Dual	0.28	kg
	Trapeze	0.6	kg
	Suspension Plate	0.14	kg
	Yaw Chassis	0.5	kg
	Roll chassis	0.4	kg
	Sensor column	0.2	kg
	Pitch chassis	0.4	kg
	Bolts	2.5	kg
	Cable	0.05	kg

Finally, Table 4-6 contains a summary of the amount of each material considered for the manufacturing of the different MAV components in terms of the functional unit previously defined. Several assumptions have been performed to complete this table:

- In the Inertial Measurement Unit [14], 20 % of the total weight was considered to be the plastic case and the rest was assumed to be electronic components. See an example of an Advanced Navigation system in Figure 4-4.

Figure 4-4: Advanced navigation system image

- In the IR Camera, it was assumed 70 % of aluminium and 30 % of germanium for the lenses and 25 % of the total weight for the frame. Regarding the IR element, it is composed of mercury, cadmium and tellurium, according to the information provided by the partners. In order to determine the proportion of each element, some bibliography was checked [15], [16] and weight fractions were calculated taking into account that detection in the MWIR and LWIR windows is obtained using 30 % $[(\text{Hg}_{0.7}\text{Cd}_{0.3})\text{Te}]$ and 20 % $[(\text{Hg}_{0.8}\text{Cd}_{0.2})\text{Te}]$ respectively [16]. Finally, the rest of the total weight, deducting the known components weight, was considered to be plastic.
- Regarding the manned aircraft, TECNAM P2006T, the engines model is Rotax 912, which corresponds to a four-cylinder four-stroke engine. As no aircraft engine with these characteristics was found in SimaPro, it was selected an internal combustion engine of a car but considering the weight of the aircraft engine.

Regarding the databases utilised to perform the inventory, most of the elements were selected from Ecoinvent 3 database and some others from the European Life Cycle Database (ELCD).

Table 4-6: MAV Life Cycle Inventory

Component	Material	unit/ component	Unit /WADI unit	Unit
Aircraft	Aluminium	718	718	kg
	Plexiglass	2		kg
	Electronics	30		kg
	Steel	50		kg
	Engines	75	150	kW
Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) and GPS Spatial dual EK – Advanced Navigation	Plastic	0.06	0.06	kg
	Electronics	0.23	0.23	kg
Multispectral camera SpectroCam VIS 1,4MP VNIR	Lenses (glass)	0.4	0.4	kg
	Plastic	0.05	0.05	kg
	Electronics	0.35	0.35	kg
IR Camera NOXCAM 640L	Aluminium	1.03	1.03	kg
	Germanium	0.09	0.09	kg
	Mercury	0.28	0.28	kg
	Cadmium	0.05	0.05	kg
	Tellure	0.24	0.24	kg
	Electronics	0.33	0.33	kg
	Plastic	1.27	1.27	kg
Integration platform	Aluminium	7.64	7.64	kg
	Plastic	0.93	0.93	kg
	Stainless Steel	2.50	2.50	kg
	Cable	0.05	0.05	kg

4.1.2 MAV operation LCI

In the LCI study of the MAV manufacturing stage, all the components of the WADI unit have been identified. However, it was considering the impact of manufacturing one unit of MAV without taken into account the lifetime of each component and the amount of times that they must be replaced along the use stage. For this reason, this section provides a wider perspective of the LCA, including not only the replacement rate of each component but also all the consumptions incurred when the MAV is being used until the end of its useful lifetime.

The most important consumption of the MAV during the use stage is the fuel for the aircraft. In order to determine its consumption, it was agreed by Air Marine that a realistic average consumption could be 40 l/h. The effective use of the plane in a year was considered 400 h/year, what means that 16,000 l of fuel are consumed each year by a MAV. The kind of fuel consumed is AVGAS100LL. Avgas is part of the gasoline family and is designed for use in spark ignition engines. The octane grade of the used gasoline is 100/130. However, since it was not possible to find the environmental characterization of

that fuel in the available environmental databases, a review was performed to find the most similar available alternative. Finally, even though the octane rating is lower, automotive gasoline was considered for the current study.

On the other hand, the lifetime of each MAV component has been estimated, as well as its annual effective use (Table 4-7). All that information was provided and validated by Air Marine. Depending on the service demand, the annual flight hours could significantly vary and therefore, the environmental impact allocated to the WADI service too. In this sense, the current study should be revised if substantial differences are detected when the WADI service is marketed.

Table 4-7. Lifetime of the most relevant components of the MAV

Component	Lifetime [years]	
Plane	30	400 h/year
Integration platform	20	1325 h/year
IR camera	6	8500 h/lifetime
Multispectral camera	6	400 h/year
IMU – GPS unit	20	400 h/year
Console	15	400 h/year

4.2 Unmanned Aircraft Vehicle (UAV) LCI

The second technology selected in the WADI project is the unmanned aircraft, which is a drone equipped with multispectral and infra-red cameras for surveying water networks with short conduits and areas with difficult access or requiring infrastructure or area scans. The following sections contains the LCI of the manufacturing and operation stages.

4.2.1 UAV manufacturing LCI

The functional unit used in the elaboration of the manufacturing LCI of the UAV is one unit on drone with all the cameras and devices required to detect water leaks.

The drone selected for WADI project is shown in Figure 4-5 and Figure 4-6 depicts a picture of both Multispectral and Infra-red cameras installed in the UAV.

Figure 4-5: Unmanned aircraft model GG-X4

Figure 4-6: UAV cameras. Left: Multispectral RedEdge 3 Right: IR FLIR Vue Pro R

The procedure was performed by following the same methodology as in the manned aircraft data gathering. All the collected information is showed in Table 4-8 to

Table 4-10.

Table 4-8: Technical characteristics and components of the unmanned aircraft

Name	GG-X4	Value	Unit
General information	Size (length)	620x620x360	mm
	Wingspan	NA	m
	Type of drone	X4	
	Number of rotors	4	
	Type of GPS module	No RTK with magnetometer	
	Weight	3.5	kg
	Payload	5.5	kg
	Type of accelerometer	3 axes	
	Type of gyroscope	3 axes	
	Autonomy	12/18 + 2 (safety margin)	min
	Charging time	< 2	hours
	Range	7.5	km
	Current age	1	years
	Expected lifetime	10	years
Materials of construction	Main material	Carbon Fibre	
	Frame	Carbon fibre	
	Propellers, helix	Carbon fibre	
	Electronics, controller	Pixhawk	
	Batteries	1,6	units or kg

	Cables	4,5	m
	Engines	4	Units
	Power of engines	330	W
	Type of fuel	Electricity	
	Consumption during flight	22 – 31	A

Table 4-9: Technical characteristics and components of the Multispectral camera UAV

Name		Value	Unit
Multispectral camera Micasense RedEdge 3	Country of application	Both	---
	Total area of application	TBD	ha
	Area covered per flight	16-19	ha
	Power consumption	<2	W
	Size	121 x 66 x 46	mm*mm*mm
	Weight total	150	G
	Present lifetime	2	years
	Expected lifetime (maximum uses)	>10	years
	Lenses	NA	kg
	Lenses protector (plastic)	NA	kg
Materials	Frame	NA	kg
	Glass	NA	kg
	Electronics and cable	NA	kg
	Batteries	NA	units or kg
	Other parts/materials	NA	kg

Table 4-10: Technical characteristics and components of the IR Camera UAV

Name		Value	Unit
IR Camera FLIR Vue Pro R	Country of application	Both	---
	Total area of application	TBD	ha
	Area covered per flight	TBD	ha
	Type	LWIR	
	Size	63 x 44.5 x 44.5	mm*mm*mm
	Power consumption	2.1 (3.9)	W
	Weight total	95	g
	Present lifetime	1	years
	Expected lifetime (max uses)	>10	years
	Materials	Lenses	NA
Lenses protector (plastic)		NA	kg
Frame		NA	kg
Infrared		NA	kg
Batteries		NA	units or kg
Electronics and cable		NA	kg
Other parts/materials		NA	kg

From the previous tables, the following considerations must be considered:

- Carbon fibre is, as can be observed in Table 4-11, the main construction material of the UAV. Most of carbon fibre is made of polyacrylonitrile (PAN) [17], and this is the raw material considered for the drone carbon fibre.
- On the other hand, regarding cable, it was considered a 2.5 mm diameter copper wire. From this datum, weight was calculated to be introduced in SimaPro.
- The engine was considered to be similar to those used in electric scooters in regard to size, power, and model [18]. This is the reason why the input in SimaPro was considered: Electric motor, for electric scooter {GLO}| market for | Alloc Def, U. Moreover, the weight of the drone engine was assumed to be like the one published by Neuberger [18] (see LCI section).
- The information about materials included in the IR camera of the UAV was taken from the product datasheet [19], which revealed that the detector was an Uncooled VOx Microbolometer. According to a FLIR technical note [20], these detectors are made of vanadium oxide. As vanadium was not found in Simapro databases, the element with the most similar extraction process and environmental burdens was searched in the available databases. Finally, cobalt was selected for the IR detector in the UAV IR camera.

In order to perform the Life Cycle Assessment, all the components and materials of UAV are summarized in Table 4-11 and

Table 4-12. They are referred to the functional unit used for the LCA, which is one unit of UAV.

Table 4-11: total UAV Life Cycle Inventory

Component	Material	unit/ component	Unit / WADI unit	Unit
Drone	Carbon fibre	1.86	1.86	kg
Electronics	Pixhawk (electronics)	0,03	0.04	kg
Battery	Battery LiPo 6S/10 AH	1.6	1.6	kg
Cable	Cable	4.5		m
Engine		26.5	106	g
Multispectral camera	Micasense RedEdge 3	150	150	g
IR Camera	FLIR Vue Pro R	95	95	g

Table 4-12: Total UAV Life Cycle Inventory (per component)

Component	Material	unit/ component	Unit / WADI unit	Unit
Drone	Carbon fiber	1.56	1.56	kg
	Pixhawk (electronics)	0.04	0.04	kg
	Battery LiPo 6S/10 AH	1.6	1.6	kg
	Cable	4.5	4.5	m
	Engine	330	1320	W
Multispectral camera Micasense RedEdge 3	Lenses	75	75	g
	Case	9	9	
	Cable	1.5	1.5	
	CCD	64.5	64.5	

FLIR Vue Pro R	Lens	32.39	32.39	g
	Lens protector (plastic)	36.70	36.70	
	Infrared (Vox)	16.41	16.41	
	Electronics	7.60	7.60	
	Cable	1.90	1.90	

4.2.2 UAV operation LCI

Once analysed all the components and consumption involved in the manufacturing of one unit of UAV, the next step consists of preparing the LCI considering also its operation stage. For this study, it must be taken into account that not all the components of the UAV have the same lifetime. Some of them needs to be replaced several times during the lifetime of the drone. For this reason, it was essential for this study a close collaboration with Galileo Geosystems in order to proper estimate the durability of each component.

The durability of each component can vary depending on its effective use and the way it is used. For this reason, it was agreed by CIRCE and GG to define a life cycle scenario considering the average lifetime of each component under the following work routine:

- Every day, the effective flight time with the drone is 2.5 hours. This value was estimated considering that, in a workday, the person driving the drone needs to go to the area with potential water leaks and change several times its position in order to explore a wide section of pipelines.
- The flights can be done 20 days/month and 12 months/year (600 h/year). This scenario is quite optimistic because it considers that the innovative technology would have enough demand to operate during the whole year at full capacity.
- Every flight has a duration of 16 minutes (this is the duration of a battery). If the drone flights 2.5 hours every day, between 9 and 10 batteries must be consumed (and recharged) per working day.
- For this study, the lifetime of a drone was considered 5 years. The lifetime of a battery is about 2 years and then, it must be replaced. In 5 years, batteries must be replaced 2.5 times (total equivalent batteries required in 5 years is about 23 batteries).
- During the lifetime of the drone (5 years), the engine and the propellers must be replaced at least one time. For this reason, it was considered that the lifetime of these components is 2.5 years.

Considering the assumptions mentioned in the previous list, the lifetime considered for each component of the UAV system can be found in Table 4-13. The lifetime of the general structure of the drone was considered as reference unit; this is, 5 years. The table below contains the equivalent units of each component that are consumed in 5 years.

Table 4-13. Lifetime of the most relevant components of the UAV

Component	Lifetime [years]	Equivalent units in 5 years
Drone (general structure)	5	Reference unit
Multispectral camera	10	0.5
IR camera	10	0.5

Propeller	2.5	2
Engine	2.5	2
Batteries	2	23

Besides the replacement period of each component, the electric consumption of recharging the batteries must be included in the LCA of the UAV operation stage. To quantify this consumption, it was considered the following working methodology of GG:

- Each battery is composed by six elements. When the battery is full, the charge of each element is 4.12 volts (total: 24.72 v/battery).
- When the battery charge is about 20 volts, GG stops using that battery because of security reasons. Thus, the real volts consumed in each flight are 4.72 volts/battery.
- The batteries capacity is 10 amp-hour. Consequently, the electric consumption of each battery is 0.0472 kWh, or 0.4425 kWh/day considering that 9.375 eq-batteries are used each day.

Considering all the above, the electricity consumption of the drone batteries in 5 years can be found in Table 4-14.

Table 4-14. Total electricity consumption of the UAV during its lifetime

	Daily consumption	Total consumption (5 years)
Electricity consumption	0.44 kWh	531 kWh

5 Aircrafts LCA

5.1 Manned aircraft manufacturing (MAV) LCA

5.1.1 MAV manufacturing LCA

The first of the studies performed in this section corresponds to the manufacturing stage of the MAV unit. To this end, the LCI information presented in section **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.** allowed performing the environmental models and the subsequent analysis. The selected method to develop the LCA was ReCiPe Midpoint (H) method v 1.08, as explained above. For this analysis, materials inputs were selected from EcolInvent and ELCD databases.

Table 5-1 shows the environmental impacts for the different categories in absolute values. These impacts were evaluated for each component of the MAV WADI unit: aircraft, multispectral camera, IR camera and IMU-GPS system. The eighteen impact categories included in the selected method are collected in that table. Those selected as the most relevant indicators are marked in bold.

As an example, the carbon footprint per MAV WADI unit is 23100 kg CO₂-eq. and the water footprint is 157717 m³/WADI unit. The manufacture of this unit also has an important impact on human toxicity indicator (25000 kg 1,4-DB), mainly due to the IR camera contribution.

Table 5-1: Environmental impact of one unit MAV manufacture

	Unit	Total	MAV TECNAM P2006T	Multispectral camera SpectroCam VIS 1,4MP VNIR	IR Camera NOXCAM 640L	IMU and GPS Spatial dual EK – Advanced Navigation	Integration platform
Climate change	kg CO₂ eq	2.31E+04	2.30E+04	9.15	27.89	5.84	32.88
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	1.79E-03	1.78E-03	7.18E-07	4.37E-06	5.18E-07	4.94E-06
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO₂ eq	109.84	109.57	7.29E-02	0.15	4.54E-02	0.13
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	14.37	14.30	2.54E-02	2.68E-02	1.65E-02	6.43E-03
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	4.90	4.89	4.37E-03	6.18E-03	2.78E-03	3.67 E-03
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.50E+04	1,891.84	3.29	2.31E+04	2.15	4.56
Photochemical oxidant formation	kg NMVOC	139.26	139.09	0.05	9.43E-02	0.03	0.09
Particulate matter formation	kg PM10 eq	43.10	42.99	0.03	5.93E-02	0.02	0.06
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	6.63	2.07	2.35E-03	4.56	1.52E-03	1.22E-03
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	3.00	2.65	0.08	0.22	0.05	2.43E-03
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	36.51	9.67	0.14	26.61	0.09	0.03
Ionising radiation	kBq U235 eq	6,581.28	6,576.48	1.47	2.40	0.94	3.24
Agricultural land occupation	m ² a	271.22	270.35	0.17	0.61	0.10	0.05

Urban land occupation	m ² a	81.61	81.31	0.10	0.13	6.54E-02	0.04
Natural land transformation	m ²	0.34	0.34	5.85E-04	7.25E-04	3.77E-04	2.35E-04
Water depletion	m³	157,717.14	157,614.87	34.28	46.02	21.96	24.48
Metal depletion	kg Fe eq	386.77	360.22	10.11	9.87	6.58	6.63
Fossil depletion	kg oil eq	6115.81	6.10E+03	2.51	7.26	1.61	8.00

The highlighted impact categories were recalculated to obtain relative percentages and these relative weights are represented in Figure 5-1. In this graph, the importance of each component of the MAV-WADI unit can be analysed. The greatest contributor of almost all the impact categories is the aircraft itself (TECNAM P2006T), as expected. Nevertheless, it is important to emphasize the impact on human toxicity of the IR camera due to the composition of the IR detector. Next subsections will show with more detail the impacts of each component separately.

Figure 5-1: Relative environmental impact per indicator of a MAV unit

5.1.1.1 TECNAM P2006T aircraft

The aircraft selected for the MAV WADI unit was already described in section **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.** In the material selection of SimaPro, a medium haul aircraft was selected from Ecoinvent database. This datasheet was modified taking into account the information supplied by partners and included in the LCI.

Figure 5-2 depicts the relative contribution of each component in the TECNAM 2006T aircraft. Aluminium from fuselage and electricity used in the manufacturing process are the main contributors to most of the impact categories, specially, to human toxicity, terrestrial acidification and water depletion. Steel from the landing gear is represented in orange colour and its impact is especially relevant in the metal depletion indicator. Finally, the contribution of the remaining components is not as significant.

Figure 5-2: Relative environmental impact per indicator of a TECNAM 2006T aircraft in a MAV WADI unit

5.1.1.2 Multispectral camera

SpectroCam multispectral camera components impacts are shown in Figure 5-3. Regarding the manufacturing data from this camera, few details could be found, so the camera was divided into 3 parts following recommendations found in literature: glass lens, plastic and electronics, and the weight of each part is detailed in the LCI. After performing the environmental analysis of this camera, results revealed that electronics have the main impact on all the considered categories (from 80 % to 99 %). Ozone depletion is the only indicator in which the lens and the case amounts up to 20 % of the total environmental burden. In the remaining indicators, their contribution is lower than 10 %.

Figure 5-3: Relative environmental impact per indicator of the multispectral camera in a MAV WADI unit

5.1.1.3 Infrared camera

Noxcam IR camera components impacts are compiled in Figure 5-4. Among the impacts found in the LCA calculations, it is interesting to remark human toxicity indicator due to the presence of mercury in the IR detector. Mercury is responsible for almost the complete human toxicity impact on the IR camera and also, on the complete MAV unit. Looking into the remaining impact categories, most of the environmental burden is associated with the electronic system and the polycarbonate used for the case.

Figure 5-4: Relative environmental impact per indicator of the IR camera in a MAV WADI unit

In order to further analyse the impact contribution of the different camera components, Figure 5-5 depicts a network diagram to graphically see how each component impacts on the camera contribution to climate change impact, which is one of the three main impacts of this camera (see Table 5-1). This diagram shows that the plastic from the case is the main contributor to this impact (36.2 %), together with the electronics (28.0 %). Mercury, which impacts in a very important way to human toxicity, also represents 15.1 % of total climate change impact.

Figure 5-5: Network diagram for climate change impact in Noxcam IR camera

5.1.1.4 Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) and Global Positioning System (GPS)

The next component by which the MAV WADI unit is composed is the Inertial Measurement Unit and Global Positioning system (IMU-GPS unit). This system is described in section **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.** and its relative impacts are shown in Figure 5-6. As no detailed information was available about its composition, it was considered to be formed by case and electronics. In all the considered environmental indicators, most of the impact is caused by electronics. The case, composed by polycarbonate, has its main impact contribution on the ozone depletion indicator, amounting 28 % of the total impact. Nevertheless, according to Table 5-1, ozone depletion is the smallest impact, so the contribution in absolute values is negligible.

Figure 5-6: Relative environmental impact per indicator of the IMU-GPS system in a MAV WADI unit

5.1.1.5 Integration platform

The last component of the MAV WADI unit is the integration platform, whose purpose is to integrate all the components in the aircraft. Figure 5-7 shows the relative impact of its components. As it was previously stated, the platform is composed mainly of aluminium. Nevertheless, even though steel has a low weight, it has significant impact on many of the impact categories, such as water related categories and metal depletion. It is important to remark also the contribution of the cable mainly to freshwater eutrophication and human toxicity indicators.

Figure 5-7: Relative environmental impact per indicator of the Integration Platform in a MAV WADI unit

5.1.2 MAV operation LCA

In order to complete the LCA of the MAV WADI unit, the operation stage must be also considered in the study. Under this perspective, all the resources consumed along the life cycle stages of the MAV must be identified and quantified by means of the environmental indicators previously defined. According to the LCI study, the most relevant consumption incurred in this stage is the aircraft fuel consumption. Besides, the lifetime of each MAV component must be taken into consideration since this will determine its durability and the periodicity with which they must be replaced (Table 4-7). On the other hand, the impacts associated with the end-of-life scenarios have been removed for the current study due to the fact that the partners found complicated to provide reliable quantitative information about the end-of-life strategies. Besides, the environmental burdens of this stage are not significant when the total life cycle is evaluated. In any case, a literature review of the most common end-of-life scenarios was carried out and it can be found in the Annex A of this deliverable.

In this light, a LCA has been performed considering all the life cycle stages from the cradle to the end of its use stage. Since the plane is the main component of the MAV unit, its lifespan was taken as reference (30 years and 400 h/year of effective operation). The results obtained are collected in Table 5-2. The orange column refers the total impact

caused by the plane gasoline consumption for 30 years, and the green columns refer to the total impact of the components considering the number of times that they must be replaced in 30 years.

Table 5-2. Absolute environmental impact of the MAV components and the gasoline consumption (operation stage)

Impact Category	Units	Total	Gasoline	MAV TECNAM	Integration platform	Multispectral camera	IR Camera	IMU and GPS
Climate change	kg CO ₂ eq	270,471.37	247,317.02	23,025.30	14.79	45.75	39.32	29.17
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	0.09	8.48E-02	1.78E-03	2.22E-06	3.59E-06	6.16E-06	2.59E-06
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	1,432.49	1,322.05	1.10E+02	6.07E-02	0.36	0.22	0.23
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	28.18	13.62	14.31	2.90E-03	0.12	3.78E-02	8.25E-02
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	38.04	33.10	4.89	1.65E-03	2.19E-02	8.71E-03	1.39E-02
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	42,980.71	8,455.90	1,891.83	2.05	16.45	32,603.70	10.76
Photochemical oxidant formation	kg NMVOC	1,659.41	1,519.75	1.39E+02	3.94E-02	0.24	0.13	0.15
Particulate matter formation	kg PM10 eq	421.43	378.10	4.30E+01	2.91E-02	0.13	8.36E-02	8.46E-02
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	21.16	12.61	2.07	5.48E-04	1.17E-02	6.42	7.62E-03
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	160.22	156.61	2.65	1.09E-03	0.38	0.31	0.25
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	233.63	185.28	9.67	1.59E-02	0.69	0.37	0.50
Ionising radiation	kBq U235 eq	81,137.46	74,544.12	6.58E+03	1.46	7.33	3.38	4.68
Agricultural land occupation	m ² a	797.37	524.80	2.70E+02	2.11E-02	0.85	0.85	0.49
Urban land occupation	m ² a	163.12	80.78	81.3	1.85E-02	0.50	0.18	0.32
Natural land transformation	m ²	0.88	0.53	0.34	1.06E-04	2.92E-03	1.02E-03	1.89E-03
Water depletion	m ³	306,534.08	148,562.10	157,614.87	11.02	171.40	64.89	109.78
Metal depletion	kg Fe eq	1,354.12	893.58	360.21	2.98	50.53	13.91	32.89
Fossil fuel depletion	kg oil eq	443,745.81	437,606.94	6,104.42	3.60	12.56	10.23	8.03

A set of indicators have been highlighted in the previous table and the relative impact of those components is depicted in Figure 5-8. In that figure, it can be seen at first glance that gasoline is the most contributing element in most of the environmental indicators. In fact, in some of them, **gasoline is responsible for more than 90 % of the total environmental impact caused by the MAV unit** (e.g. climate change: 91.4 %; ozone depletion: 97.9 %; fossil fuel depletion: 98.6 %). Consequently, the impacts associated with the MAV manufacturing are small on those indicators and most of the life cycle impacts are caused during the operation stage. On the other hand, **multispectral cameras have a significant impact on the human toxicity indicator (75.8 %)**, mainly due to the **mercury** existing in one of their components, as it was widely explained in the LCA of the MAV manufacturing. Finally, it is also significant the weight of the **TECNAM P2006T plane** on the

freshwater eutrophication (50.8 %) and the **water depletion indicator** (51.4 %). Even though the huge environmental impact of the plane in comparison to the rest of the MAV components, its lifetime is much longer and its total environmental impact can be shared among more hours of operation. Besides, from a life cycle perspective, the gasoline consumption impact is bigger in most of the selected indicators.

Figure 5-8. Relative environmental impact per indicator of the MAV WADI unit

5.2 Unmanned Aircraft Vehicle (UAV) LCA

5.2.1 MAV manufacturing LCA

Once finished the LCA of manufacturing one unit of MAV, the second technology developed in the WADI project is the UAV. The UAV WADI unit is composed of three main elements: the drone (model GG-X4), the IR camera and the multispectral camera. Table 5-3 contains the LCA impact results, in absolute values, for all the impact categories analysed by the calculation method (ReCiPe Midpoint (H)). Again, the categories selected to be analysed in more detail are marked in bold: climate change, ozone depletion, terrestrial acidification, fresh water eutrophication, human toxicity, water depletion, metal depletion and fossil depletion.

Table 5-3: Environmental impact of one unit UAV manufacture

Impact category	Unit	Total	UAV GG-X4	IR camera FLIR Vue Pro R	Multispectral camera Micasense RedEdge 3
Climate change	kg CO₂ eq	45.59	43.22	0.68	1.69
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	3.84E-06	3.58E-06	1.20E-07	1.35E-07
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO₂ eq	0.44	0.42	4.83E-03	1.38E-02
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	0.15	0.14	7.26E-04	4.78E-03
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	2.86E-02	2.75E-02	3.20E-04	8.30E-04
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	38.57	37.70	0.19	0.68
Photochemical oxidant formation	kg NMVOC	0.23	0.22	3.79E-03	9.02E-03
Particulate matter formation	kg PM10 eq	0.15	0.14	2.12E-03	5.05E-03
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.01E-02	9.58E-03	8.39E-05	4.47E-04

Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.35	0.34	1.82E-03	1.44E-02
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.84	0.81	4.13E-03	2.62E-02
Ionising radiation	kBq U235 eq	6.66	6.33	5.60E-02	0.27
Agricultural land occupation	m ² a	0.69	0.65	6.88E-03	3.17E-02
Urban land occupation	m ² a	0.53	0.50	1.41E-02	1.89E-02
Natural land transformation	m ²	2.54E-03	2.38E-03	5.42E-05	1.09E-04
Water depletion	m³	183.74	176.02	1.32	6.39
Metal depletion	kg Fe eq	76.37	74.14	0.32	1.92
Fossil depletion	kg oil eq	13.87	13.22	0.18	0.47

In order to further analyse where these impacts come from, Figure 5-9 depicts the relative contributions of the elements which are part of the UAV WADI unit. In this case, results show that the **main contribution**, again, comes from the **aircraft** (drone) **and** that the **multispectral camera** has greater impact than the IR device. Unlike the relative environmental impact of the MAV unit (Figure 5-1), the IR camera does not have a significant contribution in the human toxicity indicator, mainly because in this unit, there is not mercury in the IR detector.

Figure 5-9: Relative environmental impact per indicator of a UAV WADI unit

5.2.1.1 UAV GG-X4 drone

The drone used in the UAV unit is mainly formed by carbon fibre, as well as other electronic components. Figure 5-10 shown the relative environmental impact for the eight selected impact indicators divided by all the components of the drone. **Electronic components and the battery cells** have the main impact for all the categories. Its influence is especially significant in some indicators such as **freshwater eutrophication or water depletion**, where its **contribution is greater than 90 %** of the total environmental burden associated with the complete drone. Regarding the **carbon fibre**, it mainly impacts on **carbon footprint and fossil depletion** (about 20 and 30 % respectively of the total drone impact).

Figure 5-10: Relative environmental impact per indicator of the drone in a UAV WADI unit

5.2.1.2 Multispectral camera

The Micasense multispectral camera was considered to be formed by glass (lens), polycarbonate (case), cable and electronics. The weight fraction of each component was considered the same as in the MAV multispectral camera. Figure 5-11 depicts relative contributions of each material to the selected impact categories. As for the cameras analysed in the MAV unit, electronics represent the main contributor to all the environmental impacts of this camera. In all cases, **the relative weight of electronics is greater than 80 %**.

Figure 5-11: Relative environmental impact per indicator of the multispectral camera in a UAV WADI unit

5.2.1.3 Infrared camera

Regarding the IR camera used in the UAV unit, all its components were estimated from information available in the technical specifications document of the camera. In this camera, there is not mercury among its components and therefore, the value of the human toxicity indicator is much lower than for the IR camera of the MAV unit. Besides, since it was not possible to find the environmental burdens of using vanadium in the available databases, it was taken cobalt as substitute (see the explanations given in the LCI description). As human toxicity was the main impact category on which MAV IR camera had impact (see Table 5-1), vanadium oxide and cobalt effects on humans were compared and seen to be similar (related to carcinogenic impacts) [21]. Regarding the rest of the IR camera parts, it was considered that their weight is proportional to those of the IR camera in the MAV (lens, plastic, IR element, electronics, etc.).

Relative environmental impacts are shown in Figure 5-12 for the UAV IR camera. This graph reveals that polycarbonate from the camera case has its main impact on ozone depletion, climate change and fossil depletion indicators, while electronics is shown to be more important in fresh water eutrophication and water and metal depletion. On the other hand, cable has an important impact on human toxicity and cobalt impact is more balanced among all the considered categories.

Figure 5-12: Relative environmental impact per indicator of the IR camera in a UAV WADI unit

5.2.2 UAV operation LCA

During the LCA of the manufacturing stage, the environmental burdens associated with all the components of the UAV were quantify but without considering the durability of each one and how many times they must be replaced along the lifetime of the drone. For this reason, even though the impact of some parts can look small, if they must be replaced frequently, its total impact on the full life cycle can be significant.

In order to address this gap, the operation stage must be included in the analysis boundaries. Under this perspective, the analysis is closer to cover all the stages of the life cycle of the product. As mentioned in the boundaries description section, the end-of-life

stage should be also included in the LCA if a real “cradle-to-grave” perspective wanted to be performed. However, since the impact associated with that stage is normally small in comparison to the rest of the life cycle stages, and besides, due to the complex process of estimating the life cycle strategies of an innovative product, the end-of-life scenarios impacts were not qualitatively determined. However, a description of the most common practices is included in the Annex A of this deliverable.

Coming back to the analysis of the operation stage, the lifetime of each component, and the equivalent units consumed in 5 years, which is the lifetime of the drone structure and the reference unit for this analysis, can be found in Table 4-13. Besides, the total electricity consumption of the drone batteries is collected in Table 4-14. Depending on the country where the electricity is generated, the environmental impacts associated with its generation can considerably vary. In this case, the flights were performed in France and Portugal and thus, different scenarios have been performed for each scenario. Besides, the average electricity mix of EU-28 has been considered to check the representativeness of the mentioned countries in the European electricity production.

Figure 5-13. Electricity mix of France, Portugal and the average mix of EU-28

At first glance, it can be seen that in France, most of the energy is generated from nuclear sources (73 %). In Portugal, there are four main actors in the electricity mix: hydro-energy (28 %), coal (22 %), wind energy (21 %) and natural gas (21 %). Finally, the average electricity mix of EU-28 shows a distribution that could be understood as a combination of the previous mixes. The importance of the renewables energies is, in general, higher than in France, and the dependence of fossil fuels, such as natural gas, lower than in Portugal. The huge differences in these electricity mixes will cause big variations in the results and in the LCA conclusions.

The results obtained in the LCA of the UAV can be found in Table 5-4. On one hand, the green columns contain the impact caused by each component taken into account its lifetime and the periodicity with which they must be replaced. On the other hand, the orange columns contain the impact caused by the electricity consumption if the Portuguese or French electricity mix is considered.

Table 5-4. Absolute environmental impact of the UAV components and its electricity consumption (operation stage)

Impact Category	Units	UAV GG-X4 s/bat s/eng	Multispectral camera Micasense RedEdge 3	IR camera FLIR Vue Pro R	Battery drone	Engine drone	Electricity, Portugal	Electricity, France
Climate change	kg CO ₂ eq	32.57	0.85	0.34	226.00	1.99	283.42	56.75
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	1.88E-06	6.75E-08	5.99E-08	3.52E-05	3.95E-07	5.79E-07	5.06E-05
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	0.25	0.01	2.42E-03	3.73	0.02	1.92	0.25
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	0.10	2.39E-03	3.63E-04	0.83	4.56E-03	0.11	1.00E-02
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	1.72E-02	4.15E-04	1.60E-04	0.23	1.21E-03	5.11E-02	1.06E-02
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	11.93	0.34	0.10	569.19	2.89	1.91	7.10
Photochemical oxidant formation	kg NMVOC	0.16	4.51E-03	1.89E-03	1.32	0.01	0.86	0.15
Particulate matter formation	kg PM10 eq	0.09	2.52E-03	1.06E-03	1.25	0.01	0.51	0.10
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	3.66E-03	2.24E-04	4.19E-05	0.13	7.98E-04	2.57E-03	1.34E-02
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.32	0.01	9.10E-04	0.21	0.01	1.33E-03	1.35E-02
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.54	0.01	2.06E-03	6.05	0.03	0.02	0.07
Ionising radiation	kBq U235 eq	5.26	0.14	0.03	22.41	0.23	2.56	439.42
Agricultural land occupation	m ² a	0.47	0.02	3.44E-03	3.47	0.05	0.23	1.80
Urban land occupation	m ² a	0.34	9.45E-03	7.03E-03	3.25	0.03	2.04	0.24
Natural land transformation	m ²	1.65E-03	5.44E-05	2.71E-05	1.31E-02	3.37E-04	1.34E-02	1.57E-03
Water depletion	m ³	104.44	3.20	0.66	1,540.10	11.52	5,636.63	2,291.40
Metal depletion	kg Fe eq	32.56	0.96	0.16	943.24	2.54	0.14	3.71
Fossil depletion	kg oil eq	10.04	0.23	0.09	68.08	0.54	59.86	16.31

As a summary of the total environmental impact caused by the UAV both in Portugal and in France can be found in Table 5-5. As it was done in the previous sections, some indicators have been highlighted as the more representative ones and they have been studied with more detail. In fact, the relative impact of the UAV depending on the electricity mix considered is graphically depicted in Figure 5-14 for the selected indicators.

Table 5-5. Total environmental impact of the UAV considered the Portuguese and French electricity mix

Impact Category	Unit	Total Impact Portugal	Total Impact France
Climate change	kg CO₂ eq	545.16	318.49
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	3.82E-05	8.82E-05
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO₂ eq	5.93	4.26
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	1.05	0.95
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	0.30	0.26
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	586.35	591.54
Photochemical oxidant formation	kg NMVOC	2.36	1.65
Particulate matter formation	kg PM10 eq	1.86	1.45
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.14	0.15
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.55	0.56
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	6.66	6.71
Ionising radiation	kBq U235 eq	30.62	467.48
Agricultural land occupation	m ² a	4.25	5.81
Urban land occupation	m ² a	5.68	3.87
Natural land transformation	m ²	0.03	0.02
Water depletion	m³	7,296.55	3,951.32
Metal depletion	kg Fe eq	979.59	983.17
Fossil depletion	kg oil eq	138.84	95.29

As expected, the value of the ionizing radiation indicator is much greater in France than in Portugal due to the big weight of the nuclear sources in the French electricity mix. In fact, looking at the Figure 5-15, it is possible to check that most of the total ionizing radiation impact in France is caused by the electricity consumption, whereas in Portugal, the influence of the electricity in that indicator is almost negligible. Something similar is found in the ozone depletion indicator although the difference is not so substantial. The value of this indicator is much bigger in France than in Portugal and this is because the contribution of the French electricity to this indicator is significant and in Portugal, is lower than 5 %.

On the other hand, the electricity mix of Portugal has a big proportion of fossil fuel sources such as coal or natural gas. For this reason, the impact of the UAV in the climate change indicator when is used in Portugal is almost twice than the impact in France. A similar proportion between the French and the Portuguese impacts can be found in the metal depletion and fossil fuel depletion indicators.

Figure 5-14. Relative impact of the UAV if the electricity mix of Portugal or France is considered

Figure 5-15. Contribution of the UAV components and the batteries electricity consumption to the total environmental impact of the UAV

To sum up, **the electricity consumption originates most of the total environmental impact on many indicators.** When this happens, it is very important to establish the electricity mix that is going to be used for the LCA, because it can strongly change the conclusions.

Finally, the last part of the UAV operation LCA is dedicated to determining the effect of considering the lifetime of each component on the total environmental impact. To this end, Figure 5-16 and Figure 5-17 contains the total relative impact of the UAV WADI unit with the Portuguese and French electricity mix respectively.

In both cases, in most of the indicators, the greatest contributor is the drone batteries impact. This result can be surprising if it is compared to the results obtained during the UAV manufacturing LCA, where the relative contribution of the batteries was low. However, in that case, it was considered that the UAV was using only one battery. Now, when we take

into account the lifetime and the replacement period of the batteries, the number of batteries that must be used along the lifetime of the drone are 34 (see LCI section), increasing its environmental burden. Besides, the electricity consumption of the batteries has a relevant weight on the climate change indicator (especially in Portugal), water depletion and fossil fuel depletion indicators. Finally, the contribution of the general structure is also relevant for some indicators but always lower than 10 %.

Figure 5-16. Relative environmental impact per indicator of the UAV WADI unit considering the Portuguese electricity mix

Figure 5-17. Relative environmental impact per indicator of the UAV WADI unit considering the French electricity mix

6 Environmental benefits associated with water leaks detection

Once performed the LCA of both WADI units, this section aims at performing a comparison between the environmental burdens caused by the manufacturing and use of the MAV and UAV units with the potential benefits derived from its application.

In order to quantify the potential benefits of this innovative leakage detection technique, the assumptions used in the deliverable 9.1 – “Analysis of Market Conditions” are used. In that report, it was considered that the WADI service could be implemented over five percent of the total European water supply network. Under this scenario, the implementation of the WADI service could recover 91.25 mill m³/year of drinking water. Regarding irrigated water, if the WADI service were applied over 5 % of the total irrigated area, the total water saved could potentially be 225 mill m³/year.

If the previous water savings are compared to the water depletion associated with the life cycle stages of the WADI units, the benefits associated with this detection system are huge. On the one hand, the water footprint of the MAV unit during its complete lifetime (30 years) is about 300,000 m³ (10,000 m³/year). Even though this is the water depletion caused by only one MAV WADI unit, and the previous potential water saving was estimated considering that many WADI units are working at the same time, the difference is so high that in all the cases, important benefits will be obtained.

On the other hand, the water depletion of the UAV unit caused by its manufacturing and by the consumptions incurred along its use stage (5 years) is much lower. In fact, taking into account the Portuguese electricity mix to quantify the impacts caused by the drone electric consumption, the total water footprint of the UAV WADI unit is about 7,300 m³ (1,460 m³/year). In comparison to the potential benefits achieved by the WADI techniques, this value is almost negligible. The water leaks detection capacity of the UAV unit is lower than the MAV unit because of the limited autonomy of the batteries and the covered area per flight. However, this unit will be a useful detection method to explore areas with complicated access for other alternatives and therefore, both methods complement each other.

From the CO₂ emissions point of view, it was estimated in D9.1 that the WADI service could potentially reduce 116.14 mill kg of CO₂/year by reducing the energy consumption for the water supplying. In comparison to the total carbon footprint associated with the MAV and UAV WADI units (270,471 kg CO₂ and 545 kg CO₂ respectively), the benefits are enormous.

To sum up, the preliminary environmental evaluation performed for the WADI units indicates that the benefits achieved are much greater than the burdens caused by their use and their manufacturing processes. However, the flights performed during the WADI project in real validation pilot sites (WP5 and WP6) will determine the real potential of water leaks detection for both the MAV and UAV units. Those results will allow to adjust the benefits associated with this innovative technology and then, to verify if the estimations made are in concordance with the real detection potential of the WADI systems.

7 Conclusions

The present deliverable contains a LCA of both WADI units developed along the project: MAV a UAV. In order to obtain all the information required to perform these studies, data gathering template were sent to the responsible partners. Those templates requested information related to the characteristics of the components involved in the WADI detection units (cameras, aircrafts...), the manufacturing stages of the WADI units, and also, information related to the flights and the working conditions.

The main conclusions obtained for each kind of WADI water leaks detection technique are:

Manned Aircraft Vehicle (MAV)

- The carbon footprint of manufacturing one unit of MAV is 23,100 kg CO₂-eq and the water footprint is 157,717 m³/unit.
- The greatest contributor to most of the environmental categories is the impact of the plane. For example, its contribution is over 99 % in some indicators such as climate change, ozone depletion and water depletion. Concretely, the impact associated with the aluminium use and the electricity used during the manufacturing phase of the plane are the most relevant impacts. The impact of the IR camera in the human toxicity indicator is very high (about 92 %) due to the presence of mercury in the IR detector. The impact of the other components is lower and mainly due to the electronic components.
- When all the consumptions incurred during the use stage of the MAV, as well as the lifetime of each component, are analysed, it is observed that the fuel consumption is the greatest contributor in most of the environmental indicators (e.g., climate change 91 %, ozone depletion 98 %, and fossil fuel depletion 99 %). The impacts associated with the MAV manufacturing are small in comparison, except the impact of the IR camera in the human toxicity indicator, which is still significant (76 %).

Unmanned Aircraft Vehicle (UAV)

- Regarding the manufacturing of one unit of UAV, the drone has the greatest contribution in all the environmental indicators considered in this study (more than 90 %), especially because of the electronic components and the battery cells impacts. Furthermore, for the UAV, the IR camera does not have hardly impact in the human toxicity indicator since there is not mercury on its IR detector.
- When the use stage is analysed, the electricity consumption required to charge the batteries originates most of the environmental impact on many indicators. When this happens, it is very important to establish the electricity mix that will be used because this can strongly change the results. In this case, the French and Portuguese electricity mixes were evaluated. In France, the ionizing radiation indicator is very high because of the big weight of nuclear energy. On the other hand, the electricity mix of Portugal has a big proportion of fossil fuel sources, and consequently, some indicators such as climate change and fossil fuel depletion are much greater than in France.

- Besides the big impact of the electricity consumption during the use stage, the drone battery impact is significant in most of the indicators. This result is a consequence of taking into account the lifetime and the replacement period of the components, since the lifespan of the batteries is lower than the lifespan of other components of the UAV.

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9 ANNEX A

9.1 Manned and unmanned aircrafts disposal strategies

Airbus endorsed a commitment towards a responsible environmental management throughout the life cycle of the aircraft, namely, its final stage.

With the PAMELA project, a valorisation of 68 % of the total aircraft weight is obtained, even though new research is being developed by Airbus in order to improve this scenario, being that the major challenge resides in recycling composites and recycling parts in which materials are difficultly separated correctly.

Traditionally, aircraft have been stored in deserts, abandonment in airports, wild destruction of non-ferrous salvaged materials, or other locations considered as "aircraft graveyards". However, the significant development in the aviation sector caused a growing concern about the aircrafts end-of-life by all the participants in the aviation industry and society. Besides, the worldwide demand for raw and secondary materials continues to increase and landfilling does not seem to be a suitable long-term solution of handling aircraft at their end-of life stage any more.

Under this situation, two of the most important companies of the aviation sector such as Airbus and Boeing have developed different researching studies in order to better manage the aircrafts after their use stage since this has not been legally regulated yet. The name of the most important project carried out by Airbus in this matter is called PAMELA project (Process for Advanced Management of End-of-Life Aircraft), while Boeing founded the industry association AFRA (Aircraft Fleet Recycling Association) along with other aviation companies. In these studies, both companies show different possibilities and limitations of the aircraft end-of-life processes considering the alternatives of re-use, recycling and landfilling.

Each kind of aircraft should apply a specific end-of-life strategy in order to maximize the positive effects from an economic, environmental and social criterion. However, there is a lack of studies in the literature supporting the decision-making process about which end-of-life alternative is the most suitable for each case. Even though in the last year huge advances were done to improve the management of the aircrafts after their use stage, there is still a long way to go.

9.2 PAMELA project (Airbus)

As mentioned before, the effort of Airbus to create a general framework to improve the end-of-life strategies in the aircraft management. PAMELA project (Process for Advanced Management of End-of-Life Aircraft) started in 2005 and was funded under the European Programme Life+. The consortium of this project was leaded by Airbus and was completed in 2007, after 32 months. The objectives of the PAMELA project can be summarized in the following three points [22]:

- To demonstrate, by full-scale experimentation on aircraft, that 85 % of the weight of an aircraft can be recycled, reused or recovered.

- To set up a new appropriate standard for safe and environmentally responsible management of the End-of-Life of Aircraft. This process will cover all aspects, from storage (D1) to disassembling (D2), smart and selective dismantling (D3) and recycling or elimination of materials or parts through controlled dedicated processes.
- To install, through an efficient, competent and complementary partnership, international network capable of further disseminating the so-called 3D process (D1, D2, D3).

A general overall of the proposed 3D approach can be found in Figure 9-1.

Figure 9-1. PAMELA's 3D approach of handling end-of-life aircraft [22]

9.2.1 D1 - Decommissioning

This is the first stage carried out after ending the use stage of the aircraft. Its first step consists of inspecting the aircraft in order to create a list of the parts that could be later disassembled and reused. Then, the aircraft is cleaned and decontaminated. Besides, all the tanks and piping are drained. On the one hand, some of those fluids can be directly sold or re-used and generate benefit (e.g. fuel or oil). On the other hand, fluids that cannot be reused are disposed by the specific recovery channels defined in the existing regulation.

9.2.2 D2 – Disassembly

Disassembly can be defined as process of taking apart the different constituent parts of a system, or what is the same, carrying out the physical separation of the components. Some of these disassembled components are engines, avionics, and landing gears, among others. To do this stage, a disassembly sequence planning is firstly proposed. Its aim is to establish the order in which the components will be removed as well as sort them into disassembly families.

9.2.3 D3 – Smart and selective dismantling

In this stage, different strategies to recovery materials were identified. Firstly, the aircraft must be dismantled and for this purpose, some technologies were proposed as the most adequate tools to separate the recoverable materials: plasma torch, high-pressure water jet, angle grinder with different types of abrasive discs, chainsaw and hydraulic scissors. Later, all these materials are sorted, grouped and shredding, before going to the different recovery channels (aluminium alloys, non-ferrous metals, stainless steel, wiring, tires, and plastics). For example, some metals are melted and cast in order to generate new metal ingots that can be used in different industrial sectors (aeronautic, mechanical or automobile) as raw material according to their chemical composition.

9.3 End-of-life aircraft recycling

Recycling can be defined as any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials or substances whether for the original or other purposes. It includes the reprocessing of organic material but does not include energy recovery and the reprocessing into materials that are to be used as fuels or for backfilling operations [23]. In [6], Sousa and Oliveira enumerate four motivations for recycling the different components of aircrafts:

1. At the end of the useful stage, the aircraft still has a rest value that should be recovered.
2. The production of new aircrafts requires raw materials, capital, energy and labour. Trough recycling or reuse, a great amount of materials or components can be recovered and this way, primary and natural resources can be saved.
3. The production of secondary raw materials required significantly less energy than the production of primary raw materials. Therefore, recycling leads to a reduction of emissions to air, water and soil.
4. Recycling leads to a reduction of waste, and consequently, a reduction of land use in landfill sites.

In the following sections, the most common recycling treatments for the main components of the aircraft are described.

9.3.1 Composites recycling

The amount of these components in the aircraft structure is one of the most important. In fact, some of the market leaders such as Boeing or Airbus announced to use up to 50 % of polymeric based composites in their primary structures. The increased use of composites allows obtaining a reduction in the aircraft weight, reduction in the number of components and reduction in the maintenance costs. Some of the most habitual composites are glass fibre and aluminium (GLARE) composite or carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) composite [24].

For many years, many composites were considered to be non-recyclable because disposal by landfill was an easy and cheap option. However, now there are other alternatives to recover these materials, for example a nitric acid treatment to dissolve the thermoset resin, incineration process or thermal pyrolysis, among others. Special attention requires the latter alternative since that could be considered the best alternative for large

scale aircrafts. After being incinerated, recovered carbon fibres could potentially be used in other aerospace applications. If not, they can be used in other sectors such as automotive, construction or marine.

9.3.2 Cabin Interiors

The disposal strategy of the cabin interiors is a concern for both the airframe disposal companies and operating airlines. The cabin contains many different materials that must be removed by hand if they want to be properly recovered. The major components are made of composites based on polymers or different kinds of plastics, which are intimately inter-mixed. For this reason, the most frequent option is to send those fittings to landfill.

Towle and cols [24] identify some challenges /opportunities that still must be faced to achieve a successful recovery of the cabin components.

- Efficient Separation of organic materials from metallic and composite materials.
- Identification of the different classes of material, metals and non-metals.
- Developing efficient and commercially viable re-processing technologies.
- Finding suitably high value markets for the recovered materials.

9.3.3 Metal separation technologies

After removing high value component materials from the airframe, the remaining materials are broken up into small pieces and sent a metal smelter for processing. Since these materials are composed by a mixture of many kinds of alloys and materials, its value is low. However, it could be significant if the components could be readily separated into purer materials streams.

9.3.4 End-of-life strategies after PAMELA approach

As mentioned before, PAMELA program was developed by Airbus to set up a framework from which to establish a reference protocol about different alternatives and strategies to manage airframe retiring for the benefit of a more eco-efficient aerospace industry.

According to [3], despite the technological availability for recycling most of the materials that compose an aircraft, it is difficult to separate all materials to the correspondent material type (metallic, composites, elastomers, etc.). For this reason, PAMELA project was able to reach a valorisation of 68 % of the total aircraft weight. The results obtained are collected in Table 9-1.

Table 9-1. End-of-life scenario for the A330-200 aircraft, according to the PAMELA Project by AIRBUS

Aircraft Section		Material	Disposal Scenario	Valuable (Kg)	Wasted (Kg)
Fuselage		Composites	50 % Incineration; 50 % Landfill	0	1885
		Aluminium	85% Recycle; 15% Landfill	19882	3509
		Steel	85 % Recycle; 15% Landfill	161	28
		Titanium	50 % Incineration; 50 % Landfill	625	625
		Misc.	50 % Incineration; 50 % Landfill	391	391
Wing		Composites	50 % Incineration; 50% Landfill	1679	1679
		Aluminium	70% Recycle; 30% Landfill	25750	11036
		Steel	75 % Recycle; 25% Landfill	928	309
		Titanium	50 % Recycle; 50 % Landfill	0	2341
Vertical and Horizontal Stabilizer		Composites	50 % Incineration; 50% Landfill	0	2928
		Aluminium	64 % Recycle; 36% Landfill	90	51
MLG and NG		All materials	80% Re-use; 20% Landfill	10806	2702
Engine	GE CF6-E1	All materials	75% Re-use; 25% Landfill	8100	2700
	Structure	Titanium	50 % Incineration; 50 % Landfill	0	1249
		Composites	50 % Incineration; 50 % Landfill	0	2018
		steel	80 % Recycle; 20% Landfill	3486	871
TOTAL WEIGHT (in Kg)				71898	34321
in percentage (%)				68	32

9.4 End-of-life drone strategies

Drone is formed by two main components: the drone structure, which is based on carbon fibre composites, and the LiPo batteries. The first step after finishing the use lifetime of the drone is disassembling these components. They both must be independently managed.

9.4.1 Drone structure recycling

The main component of the drone structure is carbon fibre; concretely, a carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP). Presently, most of the CFRP waste is landfilled. However, the worldwide demand for carbon fibres and its growing market makes necessary to develop recovering and recycling process in order to increase the sustainability of an emerging component.

Recycling composites is difficult because of their complex composition, the cross-linked nature of thermoset resins and the combination with other materials [25]. However, it is important to overcome this unfavourable situation for the following reasons:

- Environmental impact: The increasing amount of CRRP applications cause an increase in the waste and consumption of non-renewable energies.
- Legislation: European legislation is enforcing a strict control of composites disposal with some directives such as EU 99/31/EC or EU 2000/53/EC.
- Production cost: Recovery of fibres requires much less energy than production of virgin fibres.
- Security of supply: Demand for virgin fibre expected to exceed supply very soon, so primary producers may be selective when meeting orders.

In this light, four recycling strategies are proposed in this deliverable: mechanical recycling, pyrolysis, fluidised bed and chemical recycling [25].

9.4.1.1 Mechanical recycling

This treatment involves breaking-down the composites by shredding, crushing or milling processes, obtaining scrap pieces that can be segregated by sieving into powdered products and fibrous products [26].

Composites recovered by this treatment can be re-incorporated in new composites as reinforcement or be used, for example, in the construction industry as fillers for artificial woods or asphalt. In all cases, all these uses represent low-value applications.

9.4.1.2 Pyrolysis

Pyrolysis is one of the most widespread recycling processes for CFRP. In fact, this is currently the only process with commercial-scale implementations. The pyrolysis process is based on the thermal decomposition of organic molecules in an inert process. CFRP is heated up to 450 to 700 °C in absence of oxygen. At this temperature, the polymeric matrix is volatilized into lower weight molecules, while the CFs remain inert and are eventually recovered.

9.4.1.3 Oxidation in fluidised bed

This process is another thermal process for CFRP recycling which consists of combusting the polymeric matrix in a hot and oxygen-rich flow between 450 and 550 °C.

In this process, CFRP scrap is fed into a bed of silica. As the hot air stream passes through the bed and decomposes the resin, both the oxidised molecules and the fibre filaments are carried up within the air stream, while heavier metallic components sink in the bed and the resin is fully-oxidised in an afterburner.

9.4.1.4 Chemical recycling

Chemical methods for CFRP recycling are based on a reactive medium, under low temperature (typically <350 °C). The polymeric resin is decomposed into relatively large (and therefore high value) oligomers, while the CFs remain inert and are subsequently collected.

9.4.2 Batteries recycling

Regarding the end-of-life treatment for the batteries, many of them still end up in landfills or are incinerated because of inefficient national collection and recycling schemes. However, they contain many chemical components that can negatively affect the environment or even to the human health.

When disposal is the only end-of-life option, heavy metals are normally treated by stabilization and inertisation in order to avoid leaching. This way, the toxicity is reduced by making insoluble or immobilizing the hazardous waste. However, and unlike recycling, the inertised materials do not have commercial value.

The most adequate end-of-life treatment is recycling. However, the diversity of battery chemistries has also led to a wide range of recycling treatments. Preliminary procedures involve removal of labels, opening of cell casings, and destroying of seals and separators by procedures based on mechanical cutting, chopping or pyrolysis. The secondary stages of recycling are broadly classified as hydrometallurgical or pyrometallurgical.

On the one hand, hydrometallurgic techniques include acid, alkaline or solvent extraction. Here, metal solutions are generated and then subjected to precipitation, selective reactions or electrolysis to isolate the purified materials. On the other hand, pyrometallurgic procedures use high temperatures to separate metals and be subsequently recycled. A general scheme of different batteries recycling strategies can be found in Figure 9-2.

Figure 9-2. General recycling procedure for all types of batteries [27].

Concretely, for the lithium batteries as those used in the drone of the WADI project, one of the most frequent treatments was developed by the company *Toxco*. In this procedure, lithium is recovered as the metal or lithium hydroxide. Initial processing of batteries feedstock involves cryogrinding and reacting with water to produce hydrogen, which can be burnt off above the reaction liquid. Other methods were developed by *Recupyl*, where physical and chemical treatments are combined to produce lithium carbonate, or by *Umicore*, whose process is based in pyrometallurgical techniques [28].